

RELACIÓN DE CITAS – María Fernanda Retana Betancourt

Última actualización: 14 de mayo de 2026

Total global de citas verificadas en todas las fuentes (sin auto-citas): 008 / Tipo A = 008 / Tipo B = 000

WEB OF SCIENCE (CORE COLLECTION)

Total citas verificadas (sin auto-citas): 06
h-index: 2
i-10-index: 0

SCOPUS

Total citas verificadas (sin auto-citas): 07
h-index: 2
i-10-index: 0

TODAS LAS FUENTES

Total citas verificadas (sin auto-citas): 08
h-index: 2
i10-index: 0

Resumen de citas por fuente, por año

	Web of Science	Scopus	Todas las fuentes
2021	1	1	1
2022	n/a	n/a	n/a
2023	n/a	n/a	n/a
2024	1	1	1
2025	1	2	3
2026	3	3	3
Total	6	7	8

Se utilizaron distintos índices y bases de datos para elaborar esta lista y fue depurada verificando cada cita individual, eliminando autocitas, citas duplicadas y citas erróneas.

SE REPORTAN SOLO CITAS VERIFICADAS, SIN AUTO-CITAS

PUBLICACIÓN	CITAS
1. Morales-Rodríguez, J., Peña-Méndez, Y., Gómez, I., Gamboa, S. A., & Retana-Betancourt, M. F. (2025). Facile synthesis of the Bi ₂ S ₃ @ rGO composite via chemical precipitation for potential applications in electrochemical energy storage. <i>Journal of Energy Storage</i> , 125, 116948. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2025.116948	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sharma, R., Singh, J., Singhal, S., & Rana, S. (2026). Interfacial engineering of biomass-supported Bi₂S₃ and Ce-doped Co₃O₄ electrodes for high-rate asymmetric energy storage devices. <i>Surfaces and Interfaces</i>, 108992. 10.1016/j.surfin.2026.108992 2. Yetiman, S., Kilic Dokan, F., Onses, M. S., & Sahmetlioglu, E. (2025). Electrolyte-Driven Behavior of Symmetric Supercapacitors Based on CuS/CoS/Bi₂S₃ Metal–Sulfur Biomolecule Hybrids. <i>ACS Applied Energy Materials</i>, 8(16), 11896-11909. https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.aem.5c01020 3. Liao, S., Li, X., Zhou, J., Yi, X., Mao, R., Wu, H., & Zhang, Z. (2026). Numerical study on unsteady heat transfer characteristics of phase change plates optimized by fin structure. <i>Case Studies in Thermal Engineering</i>, 108042. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csite.2026.108042 4. Khan, S. S., Vashitha, A., Jiteshwaran, T., Janani, B., Bahkali, A. H., & Elgorban, A. M. (2026). Synthesis and characterization of novel chitosan coated rGO nanocarrier for drug delivery 5-fluorouracil. <i>Diamond and Related Materials</i>, 113349. 10.1016/j.diamond.2026.113349

Código de colores en el listado de citas

 Citas en Web of Science (Core Collection)
 Citas en Scopus

 Citas en traslape de Web of Science (Core Collection) y Scopus
 Citas en otras fuentes

PUBLICACIÓN	CITAS
<p>2. Martínez, J., Retana, F., & Gómez, I. (2024). Polythiophene/graphene oxide thin films: optical properties. <i>Digest Journal of Nanomaterials & Biostructures (DJNB)</i>, 19(3). 10.15251/DJNB.2024.193.1198</p>	<p>1. Miskelly, M. J. (2025). <i>The Development of Novel Functionalised Conductive Polymers for the Application as a Smart Wound Healing Platform</i> (Doctoral dissertation, ResearchSpace@ Auckland).</p>
<p>3. Vaquera, E., Caballero, A., Retana, F., Cortina, S. L., & Serrano, T. (2022). Synthesis of 3-hexylthiophene derived semiconductor polymers and composites with nanoparticles. <i>Quimica Hoy</i>, 11(04), 10-18. https://doi.org/10.29105/qh11.04-306</p>	
<p>4. Retana, F., Kharissov, B., Peña, Y., Gómez, I., & Serrano, T. (2020). Effect of complexing agents on properties and stability of FeS₂ nanoparticles. <i>Chalcogenide Letters</i>, 17(7), 353-360. 10.15251/CL.2020.177.353</p>	<p>1. Cao, D., & Chan, M. K. (2024). Enhancing chemical synthesis research with NLP: Word embeddings for chemical reagent identification—A case study on nano-FeCu. <i>Iscience</i>, 27(10). https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2024.110780</p> <p>2. Chen, W., Li, Q., Zhang, H., Wu, X., Wu, W., & Xu, M. (2021). Rational synthesis of fern leaf-like FeS₂@ sulfur-doped carbon as an anode for superior lithium-ion batteries. <i>Energy & Fuels</i>, 35(15), 12599-12609. https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.energyfuels.1c01269</p> <p>3. Ariff, A. A., Supee, A., Mohd Yusop, M. Z., & Muhamad Sidek, M. A. (2025). Transformation of n-type FeS_xO_y semiconductor to p-type by sulfur annealing in vacuum and air for homostructure solar cell applications. <i>Applied Physics A</i>, 131(11), 1-13. https://doi.org/10.1007/s00339-025-09004-w</p>

Código de colores en el listado de citas

 Citas en Web of Science (Core Collection)

 Citas en Scopus

 Citas en traslape de Web of Science (Core Collection) y Scopus

 Citas en otras fuentes